

**Perception on Political Memes in Facebook:
A study among Netizens in
Chennai**

Submitted By

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PROCEEDINGS OF THE VIVA VOCE EXAMINATION

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BONAFIDE CERTIFICATE

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DECLARATION

I hereby declare that the project titled '**Perception on Political Memes in Facebook: A study among Netizens in Chennai**' submitted for the Degree for Master's in Journalism and Mass Communication is my original work and the project has not been formed on the basis for the award of any Degree, Diploma, Associateship or Fellowship of similar other titles. It has not been submitted to any other University or Institution for the award of any Degree or Diploma.

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Signature of the Student

A handwritten signature in blue ink, appearing to read 'W. A. ...', is written over the printed text 'Signature of the Student'.

Date: 08-11-2021

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Perception on Political Memes in Facebook: A study among Netizens in Chennai

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- 3** Marco López-Paredes, Andrea Carrillo-Andrade, Paulo Carlos López-López. "Chapter 9 When Memes Become a Serious Business: Memetics as a Political Communication Strategy in the United States and Ecuador", Springer Science and Business Media LLC, 2022
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ABSTRACT

This study examines the occurrence of changes in perception through political memes on Facebook. Through the focus group study conducted, we were able to identify and find memes in nature itself that do have the capacity to attract users. And the findings of this study are able to point out the behavioural patterns of voters on social media websites such as Facebook. With the purpose of finding the patterns, we conducted an investigative using the methods of research tools, and the results were that memes have become what politics is to people, and there has been a sudden surge of political discourse and narrative among people, unlike before, which led to the factor of change in behavioural patterns among voters.

Keywords : Memes , Political Memes , Politics , Facebook , Political Campaign ,

INTRODUCTION

Mememes

The term meme was initially created by Richard Dawkins in his major book on evolution - “the selfish gene”. His book was his attempt at expanding the ideas posited by Charles Darwin and many other evolutionary scientists. On the origin of species was published by Charles Darwin in the November of 1859 explaining biological evolution to a culture that wasn’t ready to hear it. The church dominated field of science at the time enjoyed entertaining the notion that human beings were “special” and that our hierarchies were divinely mandated by god.. We thought for the longest time that we were different from animals. Darwin on the other hand considered human civilisation to be a struggle for survival over limited resources while biology constructs itself constantly to find harmony within an ever-changing environment .

With the theory of evolution we have a radically different answer to life’s most elusive question: why are we here? “We are here because life wants to multiply and survive”. We multiply through reproduction and that makes one pass down their traits to their offsprings. Thus, strong genes replicate and weak genes wane before even getting passed on to the next generation. Richard Dawkins exhaustively asserts this in his book ‘the selfish gene’. “Gene” is the accepted term for a unit of biological information that is passed down through “gene”rations.

This multiplying of genes and consumption of resources is still happening on the microscopic scale but its also happening on the macro scale. We are simply now the survival machines for these genes to multiply and survive. Genes are still doing the same things that they have been doing through us since the “primeval soup”.

If a gene is a unit of biologically spreadable information that wants to survive and multiply, a “meme” is a cultural unit of information that wants to survive and multiply. Dawkins in his book, posits that because of the phenomena of the collective consciousness of humanity, there is a new replicator participating in a new evolution - not a biological one but a cultural one. These are ideas,

behaviours, beliefs that we imitate on mass and survive beyond us. Things like the ‘idea of god’ have a very long evolutionary history passed down generations entirely through our psyches. Powerful memes use us as hosts to spread via imitation competing over the limited resource which is our brain space.

They have been around throughout history. They are the means through which human beings have constructed identity, concepts and even consciousness. According to memetic scholars, memes include but are not limited to sneaker brands, a song, an expression, a book, concepts like love. The one reason for memes’ recent proliferation is the internet.

Internet Memes

If we are to respect the etymological origin of the word “meme”, these would be behaviours or ideas that spread culturally through imitation specifically on the internet. However, we also know that an internet meme is the ubiquitous “funny image” that originated across the last 3 decades that is integral to our discourse in the modern world.

In unpacking these memes, one of the first things of note is the chosen iconography. It is interesting to see what cultural images adapt well to the medium of memes. Even though part of what source material becomes a meme is completely ironic, unpredictable and meaningless, the dearth of meme fodder found in some of these older pieces of media reveals something about our cultural memory. These images in movies and shows are familiar to us and invoke a sense of camaraderie as we decontextualise our past into representations of our present.

Godwin's Law was followed by a slew of other prominent online memes. The Dancing Baby, established in 1996, and the Hampster Dance, produced two dates thereafter, were the two that stood out the most. Note chains and newsgroups helped them gain traction at first, but other media outlets helped them reach a global following. As a result, the Dancing Baby was featured in multiple things of the popular TV show Ally McBeal, and the Hampster Dance inspired a popular novelty song.

These early specimens, of course, are not always what we suppose of when we hear the word meme presently. They were underlying animated visuals that were forerunners to moment's GIFs. They were, notwithstanding, unlike anything people had ever seen anteriorly, and as a result, they got an instant marvel.

In the early aughts, when broadband internet got more universally available, internet memes began to take on the aesthetic we now identify with them. Websites like eBaum's World and online marvels like LOLcats contributed to the development of the standard picture macro used by maximum internet memes.

A sketch or a pic is displayed at the top and bottom of the image in the standard image macro template. The manual is normally white with a black contour, and it's written in all caps with the Impact typeface. The top manual builds up the joke, while the lower manual provides the punchline, comparable to how spoken- word jokes operate.

The Chuck Norris Information series, which was extremely popular in themid-aughts, is one of the most well- known specimens of the typical meme layout. The Success Kid, Scumbag Steve, and the Intolerably Attached Woman are all notable specimens.

As this last specimen demonstrates, online memes are not just screen. Videotape memes, hourly known as vemes, are another type of meme.

Videotape memes went extremely popular after the incoming of YouTube in 2005.

Notwithstanding, you will recall how popular rickrolling was, If you were on the internet in 2007. People would reply a YouTube link to their musketeers, asking them to see a new movie teaser, a controversial videotape that everyone was talking about, or a sneaker view at the season premiere of their favorite show. When they clicked on the link, the videotape for Rick Astley's 1987 blockbuster single " Nowise Gon na Give You Up " began playing.

These early videotape memes arose in tandem with the rise in vogueishness of social media platforms. Millions of people were using Facebook and Twitter in 2009, contributing variegated

forms of information with their online pals and followers. These networks, together with YouTube, threw us into the viral video period.

The idiom "viral videotape" refers to online vids that have gone viral after being partook universally on social media and websites. The Nyan Cat, Harlem Shake, and Turn Down for What were all created during the viral video period. Any videotape may be labeled "viral" if it took millions of views.

Not all viral vids are memes, of course. Virality refers to how fast and universally reality is or may be spread, particularly through online person-to-person contact, whereas a meme is an idea, deportment, or play that spreads from person to person within a culture. While viral vids like Despacito and Gangnam Style are freely characterized as resemblant, they aren't memes in and of themselves.

Social media Memes

Several internet groups are committed to producing and sharing memes in order to make a concept go viral—a technique known as "attention hacking" or "weaponizing." These online groups, which can be found on sites like Reddit, 4chan, Twitter, and others, have grown to be immensely powerful. Despite this, little is known about how memes propagate or how they impact individuals.

For the first time, University College London and a few colleagues have established a mechanism to monitor the growth and dissemination of memes over the internet. The researchers utilized this method to examine how meme-creating communities impact one another and, as a consequence, identify the most influential groups.

The initial stage in the approach was to build a system for recognizing and tracking memes. The team does this by detecting visually similar photographs and assessing how they cluster in diverse groups.

With a method known as perceptual hashing, or pHashing, finding visually related photos is quite straightforward. An algorithm is used to turn a picture into a collection of vectors that describe it mathematically. Similar sets of vectors or pHashes may be identified in visually similar photos.

The team used their algorithm on a database of over 100 million images gathered from meme-generating communities like Reddit and its subgroup The Donald, Twitter, 4chan's politically incorrect forum known as /pol/, and Gab, a new social network created to accommodate users who had been banned from other communities.

The researchers also downloaded 700,000 photos from KnowYourMeme.com, a meme library that serves as a form of ground truth for the origin and meaning of memes.

Although this database creates over 100 million unique pHashes, many of the photos are near replicas of one another. To locate relevant memes categorized by community, the researchers employed a clustering method.

They also looked at how variations and clusters evolve throughout time. Other characteristics, such as the amount of memes in a cluster, may help indicate how popular they are. They can find out which communities are the most influential utilizing this data.

Finally, the researchers examine at how the clusters are connected to KnowYourMeme.com entries. This exposes what the memes are about and how they are utilized, such as if they promote comedy, racism, anti-Semitism, or anything else.

That instantly proposes a method for anybody trying to acquire influence: establish a meme factory that creates a vast number of versions of current memes. This technique is going to deliver a hit now and again.

That may seem familiar to any evolutionary scientist. It's not difficult to conceive a method that treats pHashes like genomes and enables them to develop via mutation, reproduction, and selection.

Introduction to Facebook

Mark Zuckerberg, Dustin Moskovitz, and Chris Hughes created Facebook in February 2004 as a site for Harvard students exclusively. However, by January 2008, it was the most popular and visited website in the world, with 34 million unique visitors, and by December 2007, it was the 13th most popular website globally (comScore, 2008), with 98 million unique visits. Facebook had 67 million active users (those who have visited the site in the preceding 30 days) as of March 2008, with more than half of them using the site for an average of 20 minutes each day (Facebook, 2008). Facebook, like most social networking sites, offers a pre-formatted web page where users can enter personal information such as gender, birthday, hometown, political and religious beliefs, e-mail and physical addresses, relationship status, activities, interests, favorite music and movies, educational background, and a main personal photo. Although today's Facebook users come from all walks of life, college students continue to make up the greatest number of active Facebook users, accounting for roughly 30 percent of all users (insidefacebook.com, 2009). (insidefacebook.com, 2009). Facebook today serves approximately 500 million users, enabling them to share a broad variety of information and interact with others (Fletcher, 2010). (Fletcher, 2010).

Facebook and Political Communication

In the previous two of presidential elections in America, political advertising on social media, notably on Facebook, has been a game changer for campaigns, candidates, and political discussion. During the 2016 presidential election, all candidates made great use of social media. Research by a News agency says that in January 2016, 44 percent of U.S. people reported having learnt about the 2016 presidential election via social media like Facebook and Twitter. Roughly, 24 percent indicate they have resorted to the Facebook postings for information surrounding the election. In 2016 in the month preceding up to Election day, more Americans picked Facebook as the site they most commonly accessed for political information than any other site. During the 2020 presidential election, the significance of Facebook and other social media was significantly bigger when

compared to 2016. The two leading Candidates Donald Trump and Joe Biden spent \$48.7 million and \$45.4 million respectively for the Facebook advertising alone. Facebook is receiving significant criticism from politicians for its participation in politics, a critique that is connected to antitrust issues.

The editorial board of the New York Times released a strong criticism of Facebook's inability to limit the spread of disinformation in the run-up to the 2016 U.S. presidential election on November 19, 2016.

The opinion post is representative of worries about the risk that social media like Facebook pose to democracy by influencing individuals' views of political reality. This argument argues that the impacts of social media on persons' belief accuracy are large, as compared to the more confined effects connected with prior media systems.

Cambridge Analytica

In March 2018, The New York Times, in partnership with The London Observer and The Guardian, received a stockpile of Cambridge Analytica documents. According to the records, the company, whose board of directors includes former Trump adviser Stephen K. Bannon, used data stolen improperly from Facebook to develop voter profiles. The News prompted an inquiry into Cambridge Analytica and threw Facebook into its most serious crisis to yet. It went on to say that in 2014, Cambridge Analytica's contractors and employees accessed tens of millions of Facebook users' private data in order to sell psychological profiles of American voters to political campaigns - the greatest known Facebook data breach in history.

Facebook and Indian Political Usage

Indian society has a huge craze and trend for Facebook and its co-apps like WhatsApp and Instagram. The election campaign has got a new battle ground other than the assembly. The social media giant Facebook serves as a battle ground for campaign's to gain voters either by accusing others or by attractive advertisements. This trend rose from the year 2012 United States election where Facebook served as an integral part to connect with people personally with customized messages, voice notes etc. Many analytical companies started using this trend which emerged in India too. This allowed political parties to gain voters in their favor and increase their strength in the social media. People started believing in forward messages and false accusations. The political parties used various techniques like video messages, voice notes and personalized messages with their agendas which have covered and kindle people to favor for the party. On the other hand it has become a platform for false forward and spam messages where a group or an individual creates fake messages pages and posts which creates a false impression on the political parties. The advancement of technology has paved the way for advanced campaigns like ads and Facebook pages post stories etc. where you are convinced to vote for a party which can create a bias and change people's impression. The advertisement on social media has emerged in such a huge way that within a few seconds we are moved or influenced as they are repetitive. Facebook has not yet disclosed its earnings through political campaign's. Memes which are in trend and which have the power to influence one's decision and thoughts. People are easily moved by trending memes and videos. Some Facebook pages with huge followers are being used by political parties to reach people with memes trending videos with their agendas. Though the memes and videos are funny they are being shared and it creates a trend through which the parties either gain reach or voters which gives an opportunity for them. The advancement of technology using artificial intelligence and such things help these people to reach even more through social media through sentimental analysis. The candidates reach people through live interaction with people which creates a strong impression that these candidates are worthy and are always ready to help people. The social media polls and surveys plays an important role which creates very strong impression in people's mind when deciding their leaders as they think that they are with

the society. The social media giant Facebook has been accused for many data breaches and spam activities these have paved way for false campaign's where the parties or individual post negative comments and posts etc. on others. Facebook and its co networks are the new vital battle ground for political parties to gain voters, to accuse the opposition, to promote their moto agendas their welfare activities and etc. through these people's thoughts are being kindle influenced or sometimes make them believe that a certain party is the best but this is a serious issue of the society as all the information are not true to the whole which can create a strong bias on people society people must think before choosing a worthy candidate as he represents them and their society and leads them in the path of development.

Tamil Nadu and Facebook

The number of Facebook users in Tamil Nadu - Chennai is increasing. In Tamil Nadu alone, there are around 10 million Facebook members, with 52 lakh in Chennai. In Tamil Nadu, however, Facebook is totally dominated by men, with 76 percent males and the rest females.

This is an unusual statistic for Tamilnadu. In other states, the ratio is more even, with 56% males and 44% females, however in countries like the United States, there are more females on Facebook than males.

In addition, regardless of gender, there appears to be a downward tendency in usage with age. Electronic products, like as mobile phones, food and beverage corporations, female celebrities (again, maybe due to gender bias in the user base), political leaders, and sportspeople are among Tamils' favorite categories. This provides advertisers with insight on the types of material that Tamil audiences prefer. This should be taken into account while developing a Facebook content marketing plan.

Tamilnadu and Facebook Political Communication

Political ideas have always found a way to reach the common people. Newspapers, speeches, books, radios, and movies are all examples. Tamilnadu is one state which has used its media power to the fullest to get their ideas transported to the public. The most powerful and influential medium in today's world is social media, and one of the oldest and most popular social media is Facebook. Even though it has lost its popularity, India has the most active number of Facebook users.

Almost all the top political leaders in Tamilnadu have their own Facebook account which is being managed by their IT wing. The Chief Minister of Tamilnadu has an official Facebook page on which the daily activities and orders of the Chief Minister are being updated.

In the 2021 general assembly election, IPAC played a vital role in the success of DMK in the form of online campaigning.

The news channels also have their own Facebook accounts, which can convey the news much faster and reach a much wider audience.

There are political groups which organize various online events and talks on politics and political figures.

Since their inception, memes, which have been a revolution in the last decade, have taken control of social media. It has been the easiest and quickest way to communicate something. Even a three-hour movie can be compiled into a meme. Politicians seized this opportunity and used it to spread their propaganda and ideas, as well as to defame their opponents. Politicians made certain that memes about them were always available, whether they were demeaning or praising. They needed the publicity. But on the other side, memes have helped to bring down one's political career by making them as a joke.

The major drawback of the political content on Facebook is the credibility of the information. People supporting a particular ideology or party spread fake news or morphed photos, which create

a lot of trouble.

Facebook helps in a way to attain political knowledge, but one must fact check any of the information before believing it.

AIM:

This research is to examine the insight that the political memes carry forward in Facebook.

OBJECTIVES:

- Are memes used as a tool for distribution of political knowledge
- To analyze the role of political memes in voting behaviour

SCOPE OF THE STUDY:

This study is to determine the behavior changes in the voting pattern, and analyse the role of political memes in the change through careful investigation by Facebook users. This study can also be used as a comparative study for other states in the country, and it may also be used as a study by the researchers in the future.

LIMITATIONS OF THE STUDY:

This study is based completely on political memes.

This research is confined to one specific social forum; Facebook.

The complete analysis has been focused on the political domain in Tamil Nadu through memes.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

What Does it All Meme?: A Look into Gender Stereotypes and Traits in the 2016 Presidential Primary Campaign by Elizabeth Ann Spencer

During the 2016 Presidential election, this content analysis examines how primary election candidates were regarded on social media. As a result of Internet and social media evolutions in communications, candidate memes have been brought to the new framework of American political news consumption. Using feminist communications and media theories, the researcher looked at the 2016 presidential election and Democratic primary contenders Bernie Sanders and Hillary Clinton, as well as Republican primary adversaries Carly Fiorina and Ted Cruz. This thesis looks at how political memes used contemporary gender biases and stereotypes to frame politicians. To reach her results, the researcher gathered 550 memes from Google and Facebook groups.

It's All in a Meme: A Content Analysis of Memes Posted to 2012 Presidential Election Facebook Pages By Bobbie J. Foster

This thesis was an observational research to assess how Democrats and Republicans produce memes, employ standard media framing, and how memes fit into existing humor theories. The research analyzes the interplay between the traditional media frames of the perfect candidate, popular campaigner, and the sure loser (Grabe & Bucy, 2009) and the critique offered by Internet users to these representations in the memes.

Memetic Frameworks in the 2016 Presidential Election By Roman Kezios

This research focuses on memes, which rose to prominence as political influence tools during the 2016 presidential election. This thesis will look into the most popular memes throughout that time period and assess their usefulness. This piece will build a framework for demarcating particular forms and strategies in memetic engagement that have the highest tendency for circulation, based on Jean Baudrillard's work. This thesis will explain why some memes gain

more traction than others, based on studies on the compatibility of political ideology with memetic deployment. As a result, this thesis will highlight future potential for the development of political memetic tactics as well as their importance among diverse ideological groups that may want to employ them.

Democratic Digital Campaign Strategies in the Age of Trump: Circulation Theory, Digital Networks, and Memes By James Allan

This thesis explores the different digital campaign strategies of prominent, establishment Democratic politicians under the Trump presidency. In order to counter the massive online presence of Donald Trump, mainstream Democratic officials upped the utilization of digital memes in campaign rhetoric. He adopts a circulation framework to investigate and chart the spread of certain meme types and meme iterations across and between digital networks. He investigate three case studies of digital campaign discourse; the widely-circulated hashtag #TheResistance, Mike Bloomberg's self-satirical Instagram meme campaign, and Pete Buttigieg's "victory" speech on the night of the 2020 Iowa Democratic Caucuses. Taken together, these case studies illustrate distinctive ways prominent Democratic campaigns employ memes to harness rhetorical force while hiding the liberal ideological valences of such texts. He urge critical orators should more thoroughly account for the corporate and centralized causes of reportedly internet and digital meme phenomena.

Youth political partisipation on facebook and civic engagement in Cambodia by Sophamonyoudom Prom

This study analyzes the influence of teenage political activity on Facebook on their civic engagement involves electoral participation, involvement in policy-making, and the practice of freedom of association and of speech. The research seeks to address the subject, "How may Cambodian youth political involvement on Facebook affect specific dimensions of civic engagement sin Cambodia?" by using a descriptive analysis framework. The research states that, in Cambodia, youthful political participation on Facebook may help enhance youth's voter turnout, improved potential for youth's involvement in governance via informal connection with the government, and a more active membership in sociopolitical discussion groups. There

are three smajor discoveries in this study, such as: (1). Youth's Facebook use for political involvement, particularly before to the election date, was a contributing factor in high youth's voter turnout rates in the 2013 National Elections and the 2017 Communal Elections; (2). Youth have greater possibilities to engage in online socializing with the government, and in some cases, their interactions can effect the government's policy reforms; and (3). Existing online sociopolitical discussion forums facilitate youth's involvement in the practice of freedom of association and of speech. All in all, youth internet political participation is optimistic for Cambodia's democracy process.

Psychological effect on youth through memes on Facebook, Twitter & Instagram by Kinza Mushfiq

This research is about 'Psychological effect on youngsters via memes on facebook, twitter and Instagram'. This study encompasses all the characteristics of memes: how they began, how they became a trend on social networks, how young people started following and generating memes, through which they impacted each other psychologically, and why they were so popular in Pakistan. It also studies how much time youth spend on social networks, and what trends were followed on social media up till now. Moreover, in this study, it was evaluated how memes are employed for numerous causes, especially for marketing, and how they are taking over the media. In conclusion, it assessed which selected social networks (Facebook, Twitter, and Instagram) are frequented by youth. Also, it analyzed which skins of memes the majority of young follow and what youth believe about criticizing others using memes on social platforms. The study was related to two theories: Uses and Gratification and the Cultivation Theory. Social media has become the most active medium, with a predominantly young audience that actively uses social networks. Millions of users tag and post memes with each other on a daily basis. Basically, it is being explored how memes have become a part of young people's lives in a short amount of time.

The Evolution of Political Memes: Detecting and Characterizing Internet Memes with Multi-modal Deep Learning by David M. Beskow, Sumeet Kumar and Kathleen M. Carley

This study is about Combining humor with cultural importance, Internet memes have become a regular phenomenon of the digital age. As Richard Dawkins showed in his book *The Selfish Gene*, memes work like cultural genes as they circulate and alter through a complicated process of ‘mutation’ and ‘inheritance’. On the Internet, these memes trigger existing biases in a culture or society, sometimes replacing reasonable approaches to persuading argument. Despite their fair share of success on the Internet, their detection and development have remained understudied. In this article, we propose and examine Meme-Hunter, a multi-modal deep learning model to distinguish images online memes vs non-memes, and compare this to uni-modal tactics. We then utilize photo similarity, meme specific optical character recognition, and face identification to locate and analyze families of memes shared on Twitter in the 2018 US Mid-term elections. By tracking meme mutation in an election process, this work supports Richard Dawkins’ theory of meme evolution.

Memes and politics . why some political memes goes viral and others don’t **By Eva María González**

This paper is about Digital memes are a popular type of online political and social debate. This study analyzes how the content and originator of a meme might impact its virality. The research combines both qualitative and quantitative methodologies to evaluate a sample of political memes in Spain. The utilization of emotive difficulties mixed with more nuanced humour is vital to meme transmission, and a huge digital social capital of meme-further creator's spiralling popularity.

Political Memes and Fake News Discourses on Instagram by Ahmed Al-Rawi

This data collection of Political memes have already been investigated in different contexts, this study fills a space in the literature by employing a hybrid strategy to offer insight into fake news discourses on Instagram. From 24 February 2012 to 21 December 2018, the author collected over 550,000 Instagram posts produced by over 198,000 unique users using the hashtag #fakenews as a search phrase. The study uses topic modeling to uncover the most repeating and dominant

subjects on the site, while the most active people are identified to better understand the structure of the online communities that discuss bogus news. In addition, the study assesses the visual information that is related with Instagram photographs. According to the findings, Instagram has become a weaponized poisonous platform, with the greatest community of active users supporting US President Donald Trump and the Republican Party, largely trolling liberal mainstream media, particularly CNN, and frequently identifying themselves with the far-right. A significantly smaller internet community, on the other hand, strives to troll Trump and the Republicans. Theoretically, the study draws on political meme literature to suggest that Instagram has been weaponized as a result of an ongoing 'Meme War,' in which many members of the two main online organizations troll and attack one other in order to exert influence on the network.

When Memes Become a Serious Business: Memetics as a Political Communication Strategy by Marco López-Paredes, Andrea Carrillo-Andrade and Paulo Carlos López-López²

This Qualitative research is about The media convergence theory presents a system in which information is created by everyone and everyone, with no intermediaries or censors. This throws up new chances for individuals and politicians to interact and alter situations. Memetics is one way for achieving this. Memes have three distinct characteristics: (1) Diffuse at the micro level but impact the macro structure of society; (2) Use cultural artifacts that people may perhaps replicate; (3) Travel through competition and selection. Few study have been performed on political memes. As a result, the study problem that arises is how memes enable prosumers to connect with and construct beliefs about politicians. The new study, which is based on multimodal analysis, analyzes memes in the United States and Ecuador when former Presidents were barred from using social media. It indicates that prosumers adore public discourse memes; they exploit cultural material to develop situational jokes and make fun of politicians. These memes replicate rather than generating new messages, are topic-specific, and generate split interpretations.

RESEARCH GAP

The impact of Political Memes on Netizens via social media platforms such as Facebook provides information clearly, crucially, and precisely on the various types of works, updates, news, implementations, and policies of specific governments such as those in power by opposition political parties. There is a widespread use of these political memes all over the world to criticize and raise a voice against those in power by those who believe they can choose possible measures if they are in power. This approach to social media usage is very common in the rest of India, but it is difficult to find its traces in the state of Tamilnadu. Among the vitality in the use of memes, this study aims at the various perceptions in political perspectives in social media platforms such as Facebook, particularly in the Tamilnadu region (Chennai).

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

Qualitative research

The research methodology is qualitative in nature. This method is implemented to identify, analyze and determine the data. For the reliability and validity of the data for the whole study, this methodology is implemented. The different types of methodology are:

- In-depth interview
- content analysis
- survey
- census
- focus group
- case study

The methodology used in this study is focus group. A focus group is a research technique that uses group interaction to collect data.. This technique is used to identify and explore how people behave and think, with small number of people who discusses a given topic. This technique is used to identify the voters behavior change, and to identify how to the tools are used and to explore the perception of voters. For this study we will be using the data collected by the facebook users, which are divided into two category, such as Obsessive user and moderate user. With the data collected through focus group and to enhance the data collected and for the opportunities arise during the research we would be using the two of the research design by the Focus group.

- Supplementary

Sampling Technique :

This is a sample strategy used by qualitative researchers to identify persons who are readily accessible and convenient for them. This typically entails making advantage of geographical location and resources that make participant recruiting simpler. We picked the subject "Netizens

in Chennai" and solely utilized Chennai individuals as participants. The convenience approach was employed as a sample technique by Facebook users in Chennai.

Thematic analysis

Thematic analysis is a qualitative data analysis method. It is often used to signify a collection of writings, such as transcribed data. The researcher methodically evaluates the data to uncover similar themes subjects, ideas, and meaning patterns that appear again.

DATA ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

Thematic Analysis

Memes as new phenomena

Memes are the new era of communication and sharing emotions, thoughts, etc. They are mostly created and shared by the younger generation to express their thoughts and feelings, and they have become the voice of society (Box 1). Netizens stated that content creators create memes for many purposes, such as entertainment, and those that are concerned with society and environmental issues. Memes have created many revolutions and reforms through digital form (Box 1). Memes benefit people with entertainment. Netizens usually share their emotions and feelings through memes. While it is good that society has come to a time and place where everyone can use information (Box 1). Memes encourage people to think and create new content. It encourages people to gain knowledge about what is happening in society and what is indeed good for society. Gaining knowledge through the form of entertainment and with creativity enables our brains to give attention to it. It helps in solving social issues by providing a means through which people can hear what is happening in society.

Box 1: Memes as new phenomena

- "Memes reach easily to the audience by making the news short, which aids in better understanding."
- "Memes serve as a major entertainment for many"
- "Memes benefit people from all walks of life by understanding the content in a better way."
- "Memes are a product to gain knowledge from"

Politics is everything

Since the beginning of civilization, mankind has been greatly involved in the arts and religion, and it goes with politics. The functioning of the world requires a political institution. Without it, society could not function properly. Without the functioning of politics, the basics of society cannot be done properly or society might crumble, which points out the importance of politics in our day-to-day lives (Box 2). Participants consider politics as a drama or a play where they accuse each other in the assembly and stage meetings and join hands when they meet personally. Public meetings are portrayed as stage shows, and people consider them to be actors with eloquence in speech and acting.

Box 2: Politics is everything

- “We can't be free of politics in life”
- “Politics are something like a cinema”

Memes as a political tool

Participants commented that nowadays, memes are tools to communicate with society or even individuals as they relate themselves or themselves to the contents of the memes. The political parties use these memes as a weapon to influence people (Box 3). Social media is flooded with memes. Parties have started spending huge sums on memes to promote their promises. Parties use memes to share false information or accuse opposite parties. These help them to gain support digitally, which shows their power on the digital media platform (Box 3). Politicians spend their time and money engaging themselves with people digitally. One of the ways is through memes. These are short templates but have a great impact on the voters' thought that they have the power to influence the voters. So politicians use this medium as their voice to communicate with people and society (Box 3). Social media turns into walls and posters during election time, and each meme creator and their pages serve as a medium or mode to reach out to people, interact with them, or promote their own agenda. But nowadays, it has become a regular practice, not only during election time, we see election and party-related memes, we often see them in our news feeds as these political parties directly engage themselves in memes and content creation as society is actively watching through social media.

Box 3: Memes as a political tool

- "Political party pages are promoting memes"
- "Politicians are promoting negative memes about the opposition party"
- "Politicians are spending to promote their causes, which we can easily discover."
- "4/10 memes we see in our feed are about politics."

Involvement of political parties in meme culture

Political parties get recognition from memes, and they even launch their parties online and promote them through memes. Many parties get noticed by trolls and memes which oppose their policies. So they are caught in the eyes of people easily, and they get reach and followers through them (Box 4). The ad campaign & video memes is the latest way to reach voters. They last for 30 seconds but their impact is high. There are ads that last less than 30 seconds. These are like small bombs which have higher potential to breakdown a city. Through these video memes, they become famous and they showcase them as they are always for people and eagerly await the opportunity to help or build society to the next level (Box 4). The memes pages act as a bridge between politicians and people. Some pages are funded by parties and some create new pages and start their campaign through the pages. The followers can change into voters, and they can even canvass your agenda and party moto to help people. They have a strong influence in winning elections.

Box 4: Involvement of political parties in meme culture

- "There are political parties that we know from Facebook political memes"
- "Political parties are influencing people through video memes."
- "The followers of the pages are their vote banks"

Facebook posts as news source

Facebook, as we all know, has its own population. People are virtually connected through Facebook. The groups, pages, communities, and so on are places where society interacts with one

another, and they have the potential to include people from all over the world. The memes and posts go viral and become trending on Facebook more than on any other social media (Box 5). The viral memes, videos, or posts that get featured in main stream media, like nowadays in the news, we even get a separate section for memes, as we had before comics and cartoons. These catch the attention of all people in society.

Box 5: Facebook posts as news source

- "Things get viral first on Facebook before they spread to other social media platforms."
- "Sometimes things that are said on Facebook get featured in mainstream media."

Wide reaching impact of Facebook

Participants assumed that the artificial intelligence are being deployed everywhere to make it more efficient and give what a person is interested in so that they can engage some more time in these social media which has been proved. The Facebook uses these kind of techniques to keep up their standards and to attract people to spend more time in their apps and websites. They use the terms such as we provide user a better experience so that they can watch what they need or what they are interested in (Box 6). People are easily moved by memes and other post the Facebook which has a huge network of people influence people idea thoughts and many other things. People started living digitally they are in an hunger to increase their followers or they get influenced by the person who they follow. These helps parties to create memes or videos that gets featured in the news feeds and trolled by opposite parties where they get reach or followers or even supporters too.

Box 6: Wide reaching impact of Facebook

- "My Facebook feed pages from which all kinds of memes are being posted are suggested to me"
- "People are getting influenced because of easy access to Facebook"

Facebook memes as a medium of political education and awareness among netizens

Memes share knowledge about politics, law, and other necessary knowledge that is needed for each individual. They give a broad view of each problem happening in society. They communicate easily with people as they relate the problems to the templates of the cinema or any incidents that can be related to that event (Box 7). People have the habit of checking or verifying things until they believe them to be true. The memes from political meme pages are being shared by many. The comment section has a great place for discussion of facts and their thoughts on memes. These can sometimes be funny, informative, or even contain false information. People have the habit of reading those comments and even checking their truthfulness on Google or through known resources (Box 7). We get insights into many things through Facebook. It gets information from all over the world. People share things they think are important for society or that people around the world should know about. We get that news or information before it reaches the news channels, through which we can determine whether the media has any bias in the information shared through them (Box 7). If a person doesn't have a social media account like Facebook, they don't know what is happening in this world right now because of the current updates from Facebook (Box 7). Political memes showcase their origins and what they need to create their own party, which makes them different from others, and what kind of change they need to make and how they can create a better society. Political memes help in assessing the parties and standards of politicians. How they reached such a position is how they are actively contributing to the improvement of society and the community. We get to know their contributions to society, their services, how they have performed in their tenure, etc., which helps people to decide the worth of the candidate (Box 7). Participants stated that "We discuss memes related to politics between our friends' groups and asses our thoughts and ideas. By assessing, we get knowledge and insight about the parties and their work, which can serve as a better option to decide on a worthy candidate and party to lead society. Discussing the pros and cons of the parties and candidates gives a better view and understanding. The group's communities on Facebook with friends help not only us, but also others to get an idea about the candidates and parties.

Box 7: Facebook memes as a medium of political education and awareness among netizens

- "We are learning constitutional laws and acts from political memes on Facebook"
- "I have learned a lot of things from political meme pages. "I check if what's being said is true from a Google search or from the comment section of that post. "
- "I wouldn't have known what's happening around the world and its problems if it wasn't for my Facebook account"
- "Politically related memes help find the origin of a political party"
- "Political memes, in a way, help assess the standards of politicians."
- "We discuss and share with friends the pros and cons of a party based on these memes"

Advantages of using Facebook as a campaigning forum during the pandemic

People who attend offline campaigns have a chance of meeting their candidates personally, whereas people who are exposed to technology connect with their candidates easily, whereas people who are not aware of such things still wait for their time to communicate with the candidates. Online canvassing has paved the way for new things where people can easily connect with their respective candidates to address the issue immediately and ask questions about the welfare developments in the area, whereas offline canvassing requires the candidate's permission to meet them, and people feel insecure confessing their opinions on the candidate (Box 8). The pandemic created the hype in the use of digitalization, where many things have become online, such as political parties and campaigns, which have become online through advertising, memes, videos, memes, posts, etc. They had the opportunity to connect with people personally and address their issues, affirming to them that their issues would be resolved. So they used many ways to gain voters on their side using digitalization.

Box 8: Advantages of using Facebook as a campaigning forum during the pandemic

- “There is a difference between an offline campaign and the one that's being done online through memes”
- “During the pandemic situation, it was easier to campaign through memes on Facebook since we weren't allowed to go out”

Space for political discussion among netizens

Participants used to follow their friends because they have political knowledge in order to get a better view of the politics. So few people join some parties, and those that do share, promote, and even canvas digitally for their respective parties. They have a loop to connect with people or their friends where they canvass about their party and the good deeds done by their party (Box 9). People share memes to support their party, and they even share memes that defame other opposite parties and candidates. They only show the good deeds done by their respective candidates and their parties, and share memes which accuse the opposite parties of not using the opportunity vitally and exploiting people. These kinds of acts have a strong influence on our thoughts. It can even change people's views on the candidate.

Box 9: Space for political discussion among netizens

- "I follow my Facebook friends' individual private accounts that post memes more often than political meme pages."
- “Most of my Facebook friends share and promote political-related memes, which we get influenced by.”

Dishonesty of “Neutral” meme pages

There are a few meme pages which post political memes, but they create confusion among people. Like they post memes to support a party, later they accuse them of supporting other parties, but they say we are neutral political meme pages but post memes to confuse people's opinions. They even act surprised sometimes, like if a party funds them or supports them, they post in favour of those parties (Box 10) . Politics is a new trend that reaches people easily. Many meme pages use

this technique to reach people and earn followers easily. This way is not healthy since creating or trolling a political issue or a party needs good community knowledge and understanding of the problem. Just creating memes on viral political issues to reach followers and earn them doesn't make sense (Box 10). The younger generation are their prey as they easily fall into these traps created by parties to earn the voters on their side and to assure them they will vote for their party, so they use memes to reach them and Kindle their thoughts and emotions, which alter their thoughts on the candidate, which easily influences them in voting.

Box 10: Dishonesty of “Neutral” meme pages

- "The so-called neutral meme pages are the first to post in support of a sensational event/news. They then oppose and contradict what they've been saying. It's hard to know which side they are on. "
- "Even normal meme pages post things related to politics"
- "First-time voters are easily influenced"

Fake news in memes

Participants quoted that Memes are like knife as quoted in the proverb " Knife in the doctors hand saves a person and the knife in the thieves hand kills the person” So as memes there are many ways to communicate with the society one of the most powerful way is memes. The false information spread more easily than any other information (Box 11) . People and meme creators create or trend false information through memes and the authenticity of the memes are not tested many false memes are being created and shared by many people these fake news creates rumors and sometimes riots in the society (Box11). People believe those memes and it has helped many fake memes creators to engage themselves in these type of activities. Many useful and needed news are not being noticed because of these kind of activities engaged in the society. Many meme pages use these opportunities to get reach and increase their followers.

Box 11: Fake news in memes

- "False information and content are easily spread"
- "Fake news is spreading"
- "Wrong facts are there in memes"

Facebook doesn't influence people's political leanings

Many aren't influenced by these facebook memes but it has a potential to change the thoughts. Some see these memes as entertainment and they enjoy these memes especially they compare the old memes posted by the pages and new memes by the pages and enjoy them saying how they have changed and being biased (Box 12) Some have strong opinion on their thought and they are still with holding their thoughts on parties these kind of people aren't influenced by social media memes as they don't take them serious they just see them as normal memes which are being shared or trending.

Box 12: Facebook doesn't influence people's political leanings

- "My ideology hasn't changed by these political memes"
- "I've been using Facebook since my days at school. I've stuck with the same ideology and I won't be influenced to vote for a different party"

Facebook does influence people's political leanings

New voters are the one who are easily moved by memes as they have very less knowledge on politics and how does the party do so they share or research about these parties and they end up in memes and social media where they are given 100 of opinion or they are influenced by these memes and their thoughts are like monkey jumping from one branch to other in order to keep it

safe. They are easily exploited and used when it comes to parties to vote for them (Box 13). Many end up in disappointment after their chosen candidate performs in the opposite way where they firstly say they would uplift the society and bring the world level standard but they start performing in such a way that the people lose hope of getting new things or new schemes which will be never implemented. So they are again influenced by the same memes and vote for other candidates and the same happens until they take their own decisions.

Box 13: Facebook does influence people's political leanings

- "I see people changing their views from right-wing to left-wing due to influence from Facebook political memes"
- "Due to influence from political memes, I voted for a party believing that they would win and do good, but was met with disappointment when they lost"

Facebook trolling and its real time political implications

Participants commented that the memes that flood Facebook feeds create an identity for the person. They are addressed by their memes or nicknames. Before we had pen names for authors, now we have meme names for meme creators. They even brand people and turn them into icons or role models to be followed. It gives people the potential to change themselves or try new things to get noticed. These can even turn into tragedy (Box 14). So this serves as an opportunity for politicians to create a trend or do something innovative or comical in order to become trending or viral so that people recognise them easily, which helps them approach people with their trend vibes. Sometimes it extends beyond the limit that they are ready to do silly things that don't even make sense (Box 14). The memes sometimes create a bad or negative impact on the politicians or parties, portraying them in a way that suggests they are cruel and that if they gain power, they will exploit society. People are shocked by these memes. Some good candidates lose hope of survival as big parties use these tricks to defame the other candidates or to criticize them.

Box 14: Facebook trolling and its real time political implications

- "Political memes stretch out not only the idea, behavior, style, but also the very identity of a person (example, nicknames)"
- "Politicians get famous by trolling their opposition and netizens"
- "It's become easy to defame them, showing only their negative side"

Differing reactions triggered by a political meme

The first opinion of participants is about succession politics. People now hear and talk about succession politics, where their wards get recognition easier than the others in the party, which sometimes leads to outbreaks in the party as the worthy candidate loses his position in the nepotism. Succession politics is more common in Tamil Nadu. People here, from ward members to leaders, use nepotism or succession politics to maintain a reputation or a standard that they are only worth for this position, and it has become a common practice in recent years (Box 15). This may also refer to conveying the news in a common meme template so that people can easily identify what is happening in society. Even illiterate people should understand the common things that are happening around them (Box 15). Sometimes people consider it to have memes which are

created to reach and earn followers through which they can promote and earn a lot. Some consider this meme unworthy or just for fun or even cringeworthy because it has no information which is really about the issues faced in society.

Box 15: Differing reactions triggered by a political meme

- “This meme refers to succession politics”
- “This is a positive way of conveying the news in memes”
- “This meme is cringeworthy”

FINDINGS

The findings of this thesis are to distinguish the behavioural patterns of voters emerging from the social media like Facebook. The thesis will be useful to understand the change in perceptions of people in a careful manner. In order to understand the behavioural patterns, we conducted a focus group study, distinguishing them into different categories such as Obsessive user and moderate user. From the focus group study, we derived the patterns and the relationship between politics and memes. In a strange way, we arrived at the insight that memes have become what politics is to people.

This study explores the usage of internet meme as a technique of discourse that expresses political satire. This article explores the online meme which are propagated via social networking channels in India. The study analyzes the effect of political meme on digital natives in India and its influence on political involvement.

In this finding, we can see that people are learning through this forum, unlike the old way. And unlike in old times, people are discussing and learning laws through the meme pages, and this is the reason behind memes being a favourite tool for politicians. In a focus study group, we found out how memes influenced their voting, and people are engaging in politics in this space unlike before. Especially the way memes are influencing first- time voters. At the same time, it doesn't influence voters who aren't first-time voters.

Amongst the participants who were interviewed, majority of them express an opinion that internet meme may be utilized as a medium for communication as well as a tool for political dialogue. A Pew Research research states that there has been a rise in the number of persons who use internet, social media websites as well as the number of individuals who utilize social media websites for their political activity.

Internet meme does aid in disseminating political satire and has an influence on the shift in voting behavior, political beliefs and ideologies of individuals. Memes are no longer merely just a source of fun. Also, internet meme by media companies aids in framing problems in the minds of many people.

CONCLUSION

According to focus group interview among netizens in Chennai conducted they have claimed Humour has been used as a tactic against oppression since centuries. With the development of digital technology, online memes have gained importance. When memes originally began, it wasn't this trendy. Slowly it began to be visible in everyone's feed. And soon every field had a meme page to communicate with others. It is a really basic but unique technique to connect and communicate the idea. Soon, politicians began utilizing social media platforms to disseminate messages and target their opponents. But memes have become one of the essential instruments in internet campaigning. Since everyone, in one way or another, participated in memes, politicians found them to be incredibly valuable for their campaigns. And the reach of it is larger than television and newspapers combined.

Memes are channels that express information via humor and satire. Today, online memes have become a component of the political campaigns. Political campaigners utilize memes as a means for interacting with the internet. Paid bloggers, micro bloggers and commentators are recruited to produce content. They so form pictures and thoughts in the mind of others.

The major objective of these netizens utilizing new media for political dialogue is the digital natives. The individuals who follow these social media websites are involved in discussing and spreading this information further to other audiences. They develop and distribute material too. These folks are politically extremely engaged by like and commenting on numerous subjects and so fosters political involvement.

Internet memes have been utilized as a tool in political dialogue. Political parties utilize memes to oppose or condemn specific subjects. These memes are employed via social networking sites to spread the concepts to a bigger audience. Internet memes are largely user created but there are also the ones that are manufactured by political parties as a weapon for propaganda.

We also identified the bad side of the memes. Memes do provide the place for fakes news and abuse. In case of the fake news, most of the neutral memes page on Facebook, claim to be neutral, but their propaganda appear to be for party which they favor, and they do this by posting phony news against the one, and also distributing bogus news on the candidate, so that people might be swayed by it. Since there are no ramifications for the bogus news to be circulated, and the space is so broad, there is no mechanism to limit it.

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APPENDIX

Focus Group Interview Questions :

Questions on political knowledge with memes

What is a meme ?

What is politics ?

What are the roles played in facebook political memes ?

Are you following any political meme pages or groups on facebook ?

Are you developing political knowledge from memes ?

Questions about voting behavior based on memes

Are political parties are promoting memes for election Campaign ?

Have you voted in the past elections or will you vote in the future elections?

Have you ever changed your mind voting for election influenced by political memes ?

Meme Question:

What are your thoughts on this meme?

